

SEMANTIC NONPARAMETRIC-MODEL FOR IMPLICIT OPINION-TARGET IDENTIFICATION AND AGGREGATION

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose semantic nonparametric probabilistic-model to extract and aggregate the implicit aspects from online reviews in opinion mining. Its proposed to cope with two issues of traditional clustering models, first, the number of clusters are needs to be specified before the clustering process, and that's will generate uncoherent clusters that involves irrelevant features. To solve this problem, Dirichlet process is integrated into Dirichlet allocation. second, do not consider semantic relationship among features, and that generates lack of cohesion in the produced topic. To overcome this deficiency, a side information "SenticNet 3" is being leveraged to the word-distribution based on the graph-based technique.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis problems are beyond just classification of reviews, documents, or sentences as positive or negative sentiment or opinion. Yet the most significant and complex subtask in sentiment analysis is aspect extraction or opinion target identification. Opinion target (aka sentiment target) is the entity of attribute that the sentiment has expresses upon [1]. Two types of opinion-targets (aspects) has been conducted to being extracted. Explicit opinion-target i.e. aspects clearly expressed in the review *e.g. the picture quality of Cannon G12 is good*. The "picture quality" is the explicit opinion-target in the

review. While the "affordable" in the "the Cannon G12 is affordable" is an implicit opinion-target, due the opinion-target in the review is refer to the price of the camera, and that is not clearly mentioned in the review. Also, these opinion-targets needs to be clustered/aggregated under same cluster to ease the summarization analysis of the opinion-targets, and prevent the similar opinion targets to be clustered under two different clusters *e.g.* "price" and "affordable" are two similar opinion-targets, and they are needs to be clustered under same cluster. Few techniques have conducted the implicit opinion-targets because it relies on the semantic analysis of the words. However, four main categories of methods that have been proposed to tackle the opinion-target identification; frequency-based, syntax-based, supervised machine learning, and probabilistic topic modeling.

However, the frequency-based is relied on the frequently repeated nouns/noun phrase are being extracted as aspects and this led to the problem is that not all the frequent nouns are aspects for instance "bucks" is frequently repeated noun but it is not aspect[2]. Syntax-based leveraged the hand-crafted rules and pre-labeled-clues to extract the implicit aspects. Yet, hand-crafted rules are 'domain-dependent' because are meant for particular datasets [3]. Where pre-labeled-clues lacks the new released terminologies [4]. Supervised machine learning unpromising accuracy because the number of words that represents the aspects are unbounded, and that force the supervised machine learning to be fused with hand-crafted

ruled, then this fusion lead to the problem of domain dependency [5]. The probabilistic models are also proposed for opinion-target identification.

Probabilistic topic modelling like Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and Probabilistic latent semantic analysis (pLSA) has emerged as powerful methods for finding patterns/topics and structure in large collection of data [6][7]. LDA is parametric, and generative probabilistic-model[8]. The significant trait that distinguish this clustering model is that it is cluster and aggregate the features/words simultaneously based on the most frequent feature in the dataset. But, the current effort suffers from; relying merely on the word-frequency might generate uncoherent clusters for implicit opinion-target extraction. Because the implicit aspect extraction relies on the semantic of the words. The second issue, in parametric topic modeling, the number of clusters needs to be specified in advance, and that's also will lead to uncoherent clustering.

To address these challenges with LDA, we propose semantic non-parametric model named Stick-breaking SB-LDA for opinion-target identification as illustrated in the following section.

2 PROPOSED WORK

This section presents the proposed method to address the weaknesses of parametric, non-semantic LDA. However, Stick-breaking (SB) method [9] is proposed to be integrated into the LDA to tackle clustering incoherency. A new method SB-LDA has been proposed to estimate how many clusters are needed to model the observed aspects in opinion-target identification. Nevertheless, LDA assigns topics to documents and generates topic distribution over given aspects/words in a collection of texts. In doing so, it ignores the semantic of given words. And, model the words into a pre-specified number of clusters. This modeling process led into uncoherent clusters. To this issue, Stick Breaking (SB) method is proposed to address the problem of specifying

the number of clusters in advance. SB metaphor replaces the distribution of topics over documents (topic-distribution) in LDA to become SB-LDA. Where SB method is the process of breaking the stick based on the observed data, and that broken piece of stick corresponds the topics in the document. This metaphor called nonparametric process. And what distinguishes the nonparametric model from other models is that the hidden structure is assumed to grow with the data. Hence, the number of clusters is determined as part of analysing the data.

As far, the number of clusters are being tackled by relying on the nonparametric modeling process. The second contribution of this work is to conduct the opinion-target identification based on the semantic relation they are in. The inability of LDA to deal with word-information or the semantic of the words makes LDA fall short on most prominent aspect. That is, the infrequent features are assigned into unrelated clusters, and it does not consider the semantic of features. To this end, the external common-sense knowledge "SenticNet3" [10] is proposed by leverage Graph-based method to handle the clustering in-cohesion. Graph-based method is designed to find the semantic similarity between the features and their semantic concepts from the "SenticNet 3". Where, words are represented as vertices and weighted edges between vertices represent the concepts. Hence, the weight magnitude would denote the similarity between words to being assigned to the relevant topic. And that's would improve topics cohesion.

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